

Education after the algorithm:

Co-designing critical and creative futures

21 February 2025

GenAI Integration Challenges: Learner Expectations and Effects on Trust

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This session presents the findings of two related studies in mid and late 2024, in which **focus groups conducted with undergraduate students in several Irish universities** sought to investigate and thematise their **expectations about GenAI**

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May - August 2024, **3 Focus Groups**
Media Production Students
Dublin: *DCU, IADT, TUD*

2

October - November 2024, **5 Focus Groups**
Students from Humanities, Social Sciences, Health, & Business
Dublin: *DCU, TUD*; Sligo: *ATU, St Angela's*; Cork: *MTU*

The initial intention of this work was to establish an indicative level of familiarity, experience of use, critical perspectives, and expectations about integration into education of GenAI among undergraduate students in the author's field (*communications and media technology*).

The first study (*submitted for publication in December 2024*) found a consistent and emphatic issue with **erosion of trust** and perceived fairness from teaching staff, and **erosion of confidence in the relevance of teaching practices**, which were followed up in a wider spread of disciplines and instructions in Study 2.

Study 1: Media Production Students, Dublin

- **Group 1** (G1; n=7) Final year graduands from the *BSc in Multimedia* programme, at DCU
- **Group 2** (G2; n=8) Year 1 & 2 undergraduates from *BSc in Multimedia* and *BA in Communications*, at DCU
- **Group 3** (G3; n=7) Mix of Years 2 & 3 from *BSc Creative Digital Media*, TUD and *BSc Creative Media Technologies*, IADT
- Context: **Mid-2024**, post release of ChatGPT-4o (in May 2024) and integration of DALL-E-3 image generation to ChatGPT UI
- Caveats: ~2:1 M:F ratio; Volunteer bias in G1 where most technically experienced students were likely unavailable due to post-degree work; Volunteer bias in G3 where advertisement to participate was via inter varsity media production networks

Study 1: Broad insights

- Expectations of technological familiarity and of a broad base of experience with GenAI tools due to studies of media and technology were unfounded.
- Expectations of deeper investigation of GenAI tools in specific disciplinary contexts also unfounded - *no such use evidenced*.
- Students in all three groups conflated AI with GenAI, and both terms with *ChatGPT* specifically - often using *ChatGPT* as a generic term to indicate the technology. E.g. "Google's ChatGPT"
- Students in all three groups expressed uncertainty about how GenAI developed and functioned - and those who were most confident about describing the technology (G1, G3) were also factually incorrect when doing so.

Study 1: Unquestioning use

- Students **did not express any critical viewpoints on GenAI** as a technology or on specific tools/products, viewing these as wholly positive and highly relevant to their future careers.
 - This contrasts with previous studies of student attitudes to longer-established and more familiar technologies, which they can readily provide critical perspectives on (e.g. Social Media platforms in *Azizi et al., 2019; Hossain, 2020; Sun, 2023*)
 - When prompted with questions about "*any shortcomings of GenAI tools*" that they are aware of, students in all groups provided only surface speculative responses on two themes, and in G2 & G3 reverted to discussing positives
 - Themes lightly discussed: potential to be caught in plagiarism (G1, G2); "*problems with data*" (G1); hallucination or issues with accuracy of output or fidelity of image generation (G1, G2, G3)

“

I think people can be too afraid of [new technology] but we should be using it more because that's how we'll learn...
... it's not going to replace us - it's not the *Terminator* like everyone says.

”

Participant G1-4, Dublin, July 2024

“

You're asking why it could turn out to be bad - or how it could?

We don't know that until we use it!

”

Participant G2-2, Dublin, July 2024

Study 1: Perceived hypocrisy

- Students in all three groups expressed an unprompted **belief that their lecturers are widely using the technology while preventing them from doing so.**
 - This issue was broadly agreed and even *angrily* expressed (G2, G3)
 - Students interpreted a lack of direct policy communication from staff or the institution as a ban on use of GenAI (G1, G2)
 - Students in all groups expressed certainty about the relevance and value of GenAI to their future careers and frustration / anger / confusion about why it was not being taught about.
- When prompted about trust, students expressed and agreed that this were a major issue, and that their opinion of the fairness and relevance of the teaching relationship was damaged.

“
Our [lecturers] had a training on how to use ChatGPT for designing assignments but then we aren't allowed [to] use ChatGPT doing the assignment [...] *Fucking double standard much!*”

Participant G3-2, Dublin, August 2024

“

It doesn't seem very fair either that they [lecturers] are clearly going to use ChatGPT or whatever but they're going to stop us.

”

Participant G2-6, Dublin, July 2024

“

We're banned from using it [ChatGPT]
- they're trying to detect if we're using
it - but then why are you all [lecturers]
using it?

”

Participant G2-4, Dublin, July 2024

Study 1: Conclusions & Imperatives

- These focus groups highlighted a need for **foundational training around AI technology** - *development, key concepts, commercialisation, applications, models, etc*
- **Fostering nuanced and critical reflection** on the emergence and integration of GenAI tools is crucial in addressing the shortfalls seen and the expectations about career-relevance
- Institutional and staff level **communication of policy** is urgently required, especially where this is absent or minimal, as it is incorrectly inferred or transposed from other locations.
- Further study - *especially in wider disciplinary and institutional contexts* - is required.

Study 2: Undergraduate Students, Nationally

- **Group 1** (G1; n=8) Years 2 & 3, at *DCU*, Dublin studying: Marketing, Innovation, & Technology; Psychology & Mathematics; Applied Languages; Marketing & Languages
- **Group 2** (G2; n=7) Years 2 & 3, at *DCU*, Dublin, studying: Humanities Joint Honours; Media & Communications; Nursing
- **Group 3** (G3; n=6) Years 1, 2 & 3, at *TUD*, Dublin, studying: Tourism Management, Creative Industries, Business, Game Design, Law & Languages
- **Group 4** (G4; n=7) Years 2, 4 & 4, at *ATU & St Angela's*, Sligo, studying: Biopharmaceutical Science; Nursing; Human Nutrition
- **Group 5** (G5; n=6) Year 2 at *MTU*, Cork, studying: Creative Digital Media; Digital Marketing; Social Care; Music

Study 2: Undergraduate Students, Nationally

- Context: **late 2024**, post release of ChatGPT-o1 (in September 2024), during US and Irish election cycles where AI-related news stories were more frequent.
- Caveat: Potential selection bias in gender-balancing focus groups where larger numbers of male students volunteered in all cases except G4, but were randomly selected from. Inverse in G4 (Sligo)
- Caveat: Volunteer bias in G4 (Sligo) where local advertisement to participate added text "*Do you have something to say about AI?*"

Study 2: Broad insights

- As previously, widespread experience of *ChatGPT* (and conflation of other tools and GenAI generally with it).
- Experience of use with other AI tools in all groups - notably and unexpectedly *SnapAI*, which was reported as useful for academic work (G2, G4, G5).
 - Some familiarity with the use of *Claude* or *CoPilot* and with the existence of *Gemini*, all generally described as inferior to *ChatGPT* (and *SnapAI*!)
- Students were more likely to express negative views of the **impact of GenAI on information integrity and accuracy**, but this was limited to examples from political campaigns and misinformation.

Study 1: Uncritical use, including cheating

- **All students in all five groups had used GenAI tools** and expressed positive views on the capability and utility of these. They were again largely uncritical about the technology.
 - Some students (G1, G4) expressed general concerns about how their data was being used, but framed these as an expected transaction cost in a free tool - comparable to tradeoffs in *Surveillance Capitalism* framings (*Zuboff 2018, etc*)
 - Students did not express concerns about emerging ethical issues related to GenAI (*training data, environmental impacts, etc*), even with prompting.
 - Students in all groups claimed to be aware of incidents in their immediate friend networks where GenAI was used for plagiarism.
 - Some students (G2, G5) described strategies related to **sharing a paid subscription** to allow for better quality results.

Study 1: Similar perceptions of staff use

- Students in all groups again expressed **frustration** about why they are not being taught or allowed to use GenAI tools, alongside certainty that teaching staff and people in their career industry are.
- Similar suggestions that staff are hiding their use of GenAI while not allowing it for students. More specific references to GenAI use in *feedback* were made here (G4, G5)
- A specific incident where students were aware of a staff training event on *GenAI and Assessment* was a cause of anger and frustration (G5)
- Students in several groups (G1, G2, G4, G5) expressed uncertainty about what legitimate uses of GenAI are in their contexts, alongside references to how it is or could be used in their career industry.

“

Is using it *at all* cheating? Is there an okay way to?

[... A relative] did this course and works in [a PR role] and she's shocked we don't have to use ChatGPT the whole time [...] we should have modules on it!

”

Participant G5-4, Cork, November 2024

Study 1: Desire for definitive frameworks

- Students in all groups specifically sought clarity about usage policy, legitimate or context-specific uses, and modes of referencing.
- All groups expressed uncertainty about how - if at all - any GenAI tool could be used as part of their studies, though all groups said they had used GenAI tools at some point in the prior month.
- Most groups expressed some concern about potential *unintentional* plagiarism (G1, G2, G3, G5)
- The lack of clarity around how to acknowledge the use of GenAI, when it was used, prompted most students to agree that it was better not to discuss or acknowledge it (G2, G3, G4, G5)
- When prompted, no group could provide a certain answer on how to reference or cite GenAI tools.

“

They never said "don't use it" but then if you do *and you say you did*, are you causing yourself hassle? [...] Even where you're using it in a good way

”

Participant G4-4, Cork, October 2024

Study 2: Conclusions & Imperatives

- As in Study 1, this later study in a wider context framed a **need for foundational training that could inform critical perspectives** about the emergence and evolution of GenAI
- Discipline- or Field-specific **examples of use and good practice** are warranted and sought
- Where legitimate uses of GenAI tools are allowed and framed in a T&L context, we should provide **clear frameworks on how to acknowledge and cite these**
 - See also: *TOPIC citation model*, Mulligan 2024, doras.dcu.ie/30652/
- Expansion of these studies into other disciplinary contexts, in other locales, and as new models and tools emerge will likely provide continued actionable insights.

Concluding Remarks

We need to talk to our students about AI.

Especially while we wait for agreed institutional or sectoral policies, we all need to address the information vacuum that appears to be damaging our Teaching & Learning relationships.

Honest dialogue about how we are (*or why we are not*) using GenAI tools is a pedagogical imperative in the present moment.